

Research Article

Study and Design of HVAC System for Cooling Load Calculations

Zunaira Anum¹

¹Electrical Engineering Department, NFC Institute of Engineering & Technology Multan, Pakistan

*Corresponding Author

zunaira_anum@yahoo.com

Accepted: 04 May, 2020; Online: 08 May, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3815160>

Abstract: The purpose of this study is to determine and design an HVAC system for a university section. The design part includes heating & cooling load calculations, equipment selection, and ducting & piping. In conducting this study, the objective was to perform the manual load calculation procedure, in order to understand the complications involved in it, familiarity with the terms involved and to know what the calculation procedure. It was also planned and compared the results of the evaluated calculations with the application of the load calculation software.

Keywords: HVAC System, Cooling Load Calculations, ton of air conditions.

1. Introduction

HVAC systems use ventilation air ducts installed throughout a building that supply conditioned air to a room through rectangular or round outlet vents, called diffusers; and ducts that remove air through return-air "grilles". HVAC (pronounced either "H-V-A-C" or "H-vak") is an initialize or acronym that stands for "heating, ventilating, and air conditioning" [1-3]. HVAC is sometimes referred to as climate control and is particularly important in the design of medium to large industrial and office buildings such as skyscrapers and in marine environments such as aquariums, where humidity and temperature must all be closely regulated while maintaining safe and healthy conditions within. In certain regions (e.g., UK) the term "Building Services" is also used, but may also comprise plumbing and electrical systems [4].

Heating, ventilating, and air conditioning is based on the principles of thermodynamics, fluid mechanics, and heat transfer, and on inventions and discoveries made by Michael Faraday,

Willis Carrier, Reuben Trane, James Joule, William Rankine, Sadi Carnot, and many others. The invention of the components of HVAC systems went hand-in-hand with the industrial revolution, and new methods of modernization, higher efficiency, and system control are constantly introduced by companies and inventors all over the world [5].

The three functions of heating, ventilating, and air-conditioning are closely interrelated. All seek to provide thermal comfort, acceptable indoor air quality, and reasonable installation, operation, and maintenance costs. HVAC systems can provide ventilation, reduce air infiltration, and maintain pressure relationships between spaces. How air is delivered to, and removed from spaces is known as room air distribution. In modern buildings the design, installation, and control systems of these functions are integrated into one or more HVAC systems. For very small buildings, contractors normally measure and select HVAC systems and equipment. Similarly, for larger buildings where required by law, "building services" designers and engineers, such as mechanical, architectural, or building services engineers analyze, design, and specify the HVAC systems, and specialty mechanical contractors build and commission them [6]. In all buildings, building permits and code-compliance inspections of the installations are the norm.

The HVAC industry is a worldwide enterprise, with career opportunities including operation and maintenance, system design and construction, equipment manufacturing and sales, and in education and research. The HVAC industry had been historically regulated by the manufacturers of HVAC equipment, but Regulating and Standards organizations such as ASHRAE, SMACNA, ACCA, Uniform Mechanical Code, International Mechanical Code, and AMCA have been established to support the industry and encourages high standards and achievement [7-8].

Heating

There are different types of standard heating systems. Central heating is often used in cold climates to heat private houses and public buildings. Such a system contains a boiler, furnace, or heat pump to heat water, steam, or air, all in a central location such as a furnace room in a home or a mechanical room in a large building. The system also contains either ductwork, for forced air systems, or piping to distribute a heated fluid and radiators to transfer this heat to the air. The term radiator in this context is misleading since most heat transfer from the heat exchanger is by convection, not radiation. The radiators may be mounted on walls or buried in the floor to give

under-floor heat. In boiler fed or radiant heating systems, all but the simplest systems have a pump to circulate the water and ensure an equal supply of heat to all the radiators. The heated water can also be fed through another (secondary) heat exchanger inside a storage cylinder to provide hot running water. Forced air systems send heated air through ductwork. During warm weather the same ductwork can be used for air conditioning. The forced air can also be filtered or put through air cleaners. Heating can also be provided from electric, or resistance heating using a filament that becomes hot when electricity is caused to pass through it [9]. This type of heat can be found in electric baseboard heaters, portable electric heaters, and as backup or supplemental heating for heat pump (or reverse heating) system. The heating elements (radiators or vents) should be located in the coldest part of the room, typically next to the windows to minimize condensation and offset the convective air current formed in the room due to the air next to the window becoming negatively buoyant due to the cold glass. Devices that direct vents away from windows to prevent "wasted" heat defeat this design intent. Cold air drafts can contribute significantly to subjectively feeling colder than the average room temperature. Therefore, it is important to control the air leaks from outside in addition to proper design of the heating system. The invention of central heating is often credited to the ancient Romans, who installed a system of air ducts called "hypocaust" in the walls and floors of public baths and private villas.

Ventilating

Ventilating is the process of "changing" or replacing air in any space to control temperature or remove moisture, odors, smoke, heat, dust and airborne bacteria. Ventilation includes both the exchange of air to the outside as well as circulation of air within the building. It is one of the most important factors for maintaining acceptable indoor air quality in buildings. Methods for ventilating a building may be divided into mechanical/forced and natural types. Ventilation is used to remove unpleasant smells and excessive moisture, introduce outside air, and to keep interior building air circulating, to prevent stagnation of the interior air [10].

Mechanical or forced ventilation

"Mechanical" or "forced" ventilation is used to control indoor air quality. Excess humidity, odors, and contaminants can often be controlled via dilution or replacement with outside air. However, in humid climates much energy is required to remove excess moisture from ventilation air. Kitchens and bathrooms typically have mechanical exhaust to control odors and sometimes humidity. Factors in the design of such systems include the flow rate (which is a function of the

fan speed and exhaust vent size) and noise level [11]. If the ducting's for the fans traverse unheated space, then the ducting should be insulated as well to prevent condensation on the ducting. Direct drive fans are available for many applications, and can reduce maintenance needs. Ceiling fans and table/floor fans circulate air within a room for the purpose of reducing the perceived temperature because of evaporation of perspiration on the skin of the occupants. Because hot air rises, ceiling fans may be used to keep a room warmer in the winter by circulating the warm stratified air from the ceiling to the floor. Ceiling fans do not provide ventilation as defined as the introduction of outside air [12].

Natural ventilation

Natural ventilation is the ventilation of a building with outside air without the use of a fan or other mechanical system. It can be achieved with operable windows when the spaces to ventilate are small and the architecture permits. In more complex systems warm air in the building can be allowed to rise and flow out upper openings to the outside (stack effect) thus forcing cool outside air to be drawn into the building naturally through openings in the lower areas. These systems use very little energy but care must be taken to ensure the occupants' comfort. In warm or humid months, in many climates, maintaining thermal comfort via solely natural ventilation may not be possible so conventional air conditioning systems are used as backups. Air-side economizers perform the same function as natural ventilation, but use mechanical systems' fans, ducts, dampers, and control systems to introduce and distribute cool outdoor air when appropriate.

Air-conditioning

Air conditioning and refrigeration are provided through the removal of heat. The definition of cold is the absence of heat and all air conditioning systems work on this basic principle. Heat can be removed through the process of radiation, convection, and conduction using mediums such as water, air, ice, and chemicals referred to as refrigerants. In order to remove heat from something, you simply need to provide a medium that is colder—this is how all air conditioning and refrigeration systems work.

An air conditioning system, or a standalone air conditioner, provides cooling, ventilation, and humidity control for all or part of a house or building. The refrigerant provides cooling through a process called the refrigeration cycle. The refrigeration cycle consists of four essential elements to create a cooling effect. A compressor provides compression for the system. This compression causes the cooling vapor to heat up. The compressed vapor is then cooled by heat exchange with

the outside air, so that the vapor condenses to a fluid, in the condenser. The fluid is then pumped to the inside of the building, where it enters an evaporator. In this evaporator, small spray nozzles spray the cooling fluid into a chamber, where the pressure drops and the fluid evaporates. Since the evaporation absorbs heat from the surroundings, the surroundings cool off, and thus the evaporator absorbs or adds heat to the system. The vapor is then returned to the compressor. A metering device acts as a restriction in the system at the evaporator to ensure that the heat being absorbed by the system is absorbed at the proper rate. Central, 'all-air' air conditioning systems are often installed in modern residences, offices, and public buildings, but are difficult to retrofit (install in a building that was not designed to receive it) because of the bulky air ducts required. A duct system must be carefully maintained to prevent the growth of pathogenic bacteria in the ducts. An alternative to large ducts to carry the needed air to heat or cool an area is the use of remote fan coils or split systems. These systems, although most often seen in residential applications, are gaining popularity in small commercial buildings. The coil is connected to a remote condenser unit using piping instead of ducts [13].

Dehumidification in an air conditioning system is provided by the evaporator. Since the evaporator operates at a temperature below dew point, moisture is collected at the evaporator. This moisture is collected at the bottom of the evaporator in a condensate pan and removed by piping it to a central drain or onto the ground outside. A dehumidifier is an air-conditioner-like device that controls the humidity of a room or building. They are often employed in basements which have a higher relative humidity because of their lower temperature (and propensity for damp floors and walls). In food retailing establishments, large open chiller cabinets are highly effective at dehumidifying the internal air. Conversely, a humidifier increases the humidity of a building. Air-conditioned buildings often have sealed windows, because open windows would disrupt the attempts of the HVAC system to maintain constant indoor air conditions.

2. Methodology

Cooling load calculation procedure

The heat lost from a room at any instant is equal to heating load at that time. With cooling, the situation is more complex. The amount of heat that must be removed (cooling load) is not equal to the amount of heat received at a given time.

Figure 1 Heat flow diagram showing building heat gain, heat storage, and cooling load

Room heat gain

The heat gain components that contribute to the room cooling load consist of the following (Figure 2).

1. Conduction through exterior walls, roof, and glass
2. Conduction through interior partitions, ceilings, and floors
3. Solar radiation through glass
4. Lighting
5. People
6. Equipment
7. Heat from infiltration of outside air through openings

Figure 2 Room heat gain components, Q

Conduction through exterior structure

The cooling loads caused by conduction heat gains through the exterior roof, walls, and glass are each found from the following equation:

$$Q = U \times A \times CLTDc$$

Where

Q = cooling load for roof, wall, or glass (BTU/hr)

U = overall heat transfer coefficient for roof, wall, or glass (BTU/hr-ft²-F)

A = area of roof, wall, or glass, ft²

CLTDc = corrected cooling load temperature difference, F

The cooling load temperature difference (CLTD) is not the actual temperature difference between the outdoor and indoor air. It is a modified value that accounts for the heat storage/time lag effects.

If the actual condition differs from any of the above, the CLTD must be corrected as follows:

$$CLTDc = CLTD + LM + (78 - tR) + (ta - 85)$$

CLTDc = corrected value of CLTD, F

CLTD = temperature from table

LM = correction for latitude and month, from table

tR = room temperature, F

ta = average outside temperature on a design day, F

The temperature ta can be found as follows:

$$ta = to - (DR/2)$$

Where

to = outside design dry bulb temperature, F

DR = daily temperature range, F

Both to and DR (the daily temperature range) are found in table

Tables include U-values for the roofs and walls described. However, the values of U can be calculated from individual R – values.

The hours listed in tables are solar time. This is approximately equal to standard time. We have to add one hour for daylight savings time.

Conduction through interior structure

The heat which flows from interior unconditioned spaces to the conditioned space through partitions, floors, and ceilings can be found from the equation

$$Q = U \times A \times TD$$

Where

Q = heat gain (cooling load) through partition, floor, or ceiling, BTU/hr

U = overall heat transfer coefficient for partition, floor, or ceiling, BTU/hr-ft²-F

A = area of partition, floor, or ceiling, ft²

TD = temperature difference between conditioned and unconditioned space, F

If the temperature of the unconditioned space is not known, an approximation often used is to assume that it is at 5 F less than the outdoor temperature.

Spaces with heat sources, such as boiler rooms, may be at much higher temperature.

2.5. Solar radiation through glass

Radiant energy from the sun passes through transparent materials such as glass and becomes a heat gain to the room. Its value varies with time, orientation, shielding, and storage effect. The solar cooling load can be found from the following equation:

$$Q = SHGF \times A \times SC \times CLF$$

Where

Q = solar radiation cooling load for glass, BTU/hr

SHGF = maximum solar heat gain factor, BTU/hr-ft²

A = area of glass, ft²

SC = shading coefficient.

CLF = cooling load factor for glass

The maximum solar heat gain factor (SHGF) is the maximum solar heat gain through single clear glass at a given month, orientation, and latitude.

The equation for determining cooling load due to heat gain from lighting is

$$Q = 3.4 \times W \times BF \times CLF$$

Where

Q = cooling load from lighting, BTU/hr

W = lighting capacity, watts

BF = ballast factor

CLF = cooling load factor for lighting

The heat gain from people is composed of two parts, sensible heat and latent heat resulting from perception. Some of the sensible heat may be absorbed by the heat storage effect, but not the latent heat. The equations for latent heat gain from people are

$$Q_s = q_s \times n \times \text{CLF}$$

$$Q_l = q_l \times n$$

Where

Q_s, Q_l = sensible and latent heat gains (loads)

q_s, q_l = sensible and latent heat gain per person

n = number of people

CLF = cooling load factor for people

The conditioned air flowing through ducts will heat from the surroundings. If the duct passes through conditioned spaces, the heat gain results in a useful cooling effect, but for the ducts passing through unconditioned spaces it is a loss of sensible heat that must be added to the BSCL. The heat gain can be calculated from the heat transfer equation:

$$Q = U \times A \times \text{TD}$$

Where

Q = duct heat gain, BTU/hr

U = overall coefficient of heat transfer, BTU/hr

A = temperature difference between air in duct and surrounding air, F

It is recommended that cold air ducts passing through unconditioned areas be insulated to at least an overall value of R-4 ($U = 0.25$). If there is significant heat gain to return air ducts, it should also be calculated, but it is only added to the CSCL, not to BSCL. Although the heat gain to supply ducts in conditioned spaces is not wasted, care should be taken that it does not affect the distribution of cooling. If there is a long run of duct with a number of outlets, the heat gain in the first sections of duct might be enough so that the air temperature at the last outlets is too high. In this case, it might be useful to insulate the duct even-though it is in the conditioned area.

3. Results and Discussion

Cooling load calculations

Design criteria

Outside design conditions

Location: Multan City

Latitude: 28 °

Winter dry bulb at 99%=38 °F

Summer dry bulb at 1%=116.6 °F

Summer wet bulb at 1%=82 °F

Summer daily range=14 °F

Inside design conditions

Dry bulb temperature = 75 °F

Relative humidity, RH=50%

Lighting load: 2 watt/SFT

Lighting load for main corridor: 1watt /SFT

Heat transmission coefficient (u factor) calculation:

Exposed roof: (11 inches)

Items	Reference tables	Explanation & notes			
		Construction (heat flow up)	Thickness (inches)	Resistance per inch	Resistance (r)
U (winter)	3.3	inside air film(still air)	---	--	0.61
	3.1	Inside plaster	0.5	0.2	0.1
	3.1	Slab (RCC)	6	0.08	0.48
	3.1	Mud	3	0.2	0.6
	3.1	Brick tile	1.5	0.2	0.3
	3.3	Outside air film	---	---	0.17

Total thermal resistance = 2.26

Heat transmission coefficient for external roof in winter, $U=1/R = 0.44 \text{ Btu/hr-ft}^2\text{-}^\circ\text{F}$

Items	Reference tables	Explanation & notes			
		Construction (heat flow up)	Thickness (inches)	Resistance per inch	Resistance (r)
U (summer)	3.3	inside air film(still air)	---	--	0.92
	3.1	Inside plaster	0.5	0.2	0.1
	3.1	Slab	6	0.08	0.48
	3.1	Mud	3	0.2	0.6
	3.1	Brick tile	1.5	0.2	0.3
	3.3	Outside air film	---	---	0.25

Total thermal resistance = 2.65

Heat transmission coefficient for external roof in summer, $U=1/R = 0.37 \text{ Btu/hr-ft}^2\text{-}^\circ\text{F}$

First floor:

Reception room:

Exposed wall (3.6feet=43.2 inches): west and east:

Items	Reference tables	Explanation & notes			
U (winter)		Construction (heat flow up)	Thickness (inches)	Resistance per inch	Resistance (r)
	3.3	inside air film(still air)	---	--	0.68
	3.1	Inside plaster	0.5	0.2	0.1
	3.1	Common brick	2(13.5)	0.2	5.4
	3.1	Outside plaster	1.5	0.2	0.3
	3.3	Outside air film			0.17
	3.1	Brick face	2.5	0.11	0.275
3.3	Air gap	11.7	0.68	7.956	

Total thermal resistance = 14.881, Heat transmission coefficient for exposed wall in summer,

$U=1/R = 0.06719 \text{ Btu/hr-ft}^2\text{-}^\circ\text{F}$

Items	Reference tables	Explanation & notes			
U (summer)		Construction (heat flow up)	Thickness (inches)	Resistance per inch	Resistance (r)
	3.3	inside air film(still air)	---	--	0.68
	3.1	Inside plaster	0.5	0.2	0.1
	3.1	Common brick	2(13.5)	0.2	5.4
	3.1	Outside plaster	1.5	0.2	0.3
	3.3	Outside air film			0.25
	3.1	Brick face	2.5	0.11	0.275
3.3	Air gap	11.7	0.68	7.956	

Total thermal resistance = 14.961, Heat transmission coefficient for exposed wall in summer,

$U=1/R = 0.06684 \text{ Btu/hr-ft}^2\text{-}^\circ\text{F}$

Inside wall (1.2feet=14.4 inches):

Items	Reference tables	Explanation & notes			
U (summer)		Construction (heat flow up)	Thickness (inches)	Resistance per inch	Resistance (r)
	3.3	inside air film(still air)	---	--	0.68
	3.1	Inside plaster	0.45	0.2	0.09
	3.1	Common brick	13.5	0.2	2.7
	3.1	Outside plaster	0.45	0.2	0.09
	3.3	Outside air film	---	---	0.25

Total thermal resistance = 3.81

Heat transmission coefficient for external roof in winter, $U=1/R = 0.2624 \text{ Btu/hr-ft}^2\text{-}^\circ\text{F}$

Exposed wall (1.2feet=14.4 inches): north

Items	Reference tables	Explanation & notes			
U (summer)		Construction (heat flow up)	Thickness (inches)	Resistance per inch	Resistance (r)
	3.3	inside air film(still air)	---	--	0.68
	3.1	Inside plaster	0.9	0.2	0.18
	3.1	Common brick	9	0.2	1.8
	3.1	Outside plaster	2	0.2	0.04
	3.3	Outside air film Brick face	<u>2.5</u>	<u>0.11</u>	0.25 0.275

Total thermal resistance = 3.585, Heat transmission coefficient for exposed wall in summer,

$$U=1/R = 0.2789 \text{ Btu/hr-ft}^2\text{-}^\circ\text{F}$$

Inside wall (10.2 inches):

Items	Reference tables	Explanation & notes			
U (summer)		Construction (heat flow up)	Thickness (inches)	Resistance per inch	Resistance (r)
	3.3	inside air film(still air)	---	--	0.68
	3.1	Inside plaster	0.6	0.2	0.12
	3.1	Common brick	9	0.2	1.8
	3.1	Outside plaster	0.6	0.2	0.12
	3.3	Outside air film	---	---	0.25

Total thermal resistance = 2.97, Heat transmission coefficient for exposed wall in summer,

$$U=1/R= 0.3367 \text{ Btu/hr-ft}^2\text{-}^\circ\text{F}$$

Inside wall (1.25feet=15 inches):

Items	Reference tables	Explanation & notes			
U (summer)		Construction (heat flow up)	Thickness (inches)	Resistance per inch	Resistance (r)
	3.3	inside air film(still air)	---	--	0.68
	3.1	Inside plaster	0.75	0.2	0.15
	3.1	Common brick	13.5	0.2	2.7
	3.1	Outside plaster	0.75	0.2	0.15
	3.3	Outside air film	---	---	0.25

Total thermal resistance = 3.93, Heat transmission coefficient for exposed wall in summer,

$$U=1/R = 0.2544 \text{ Btu/hr-ft}^2\text{-}^\circ\text{F}$$

Items	Reference tables	Explanation & notes			
U (winter)		Construction (heat flow up)	Thickness (inches)	Resistance per inch	Resistance (r)
	3.3	inside air film(still air)	---	--	0.68
	3.1	Inside plaster	0.75	0.2	0.15
	3.1	Common brick	13.5	0.2	2.7
	3.1	Outside plaster	0.75	0.2	0.15
	3.3	Outside air film	---	---	0.17

Total thermal resistance = 3.85, Heat transmission coefficient for exposed wall in summer,

$$U=1/R = 0.2610 \text{ Btu/hr-ft}^2\text{-}^\circ\text{F}$$

$$\text{Total cooling load: } = 76895 \text{ Btu/hr} = 76895 / 12000 = 6.4 \text{ TR}$$

$$\text{Add 15\%F.O.S} = 6.4 \times 1.15$$

$$\text{Total cooling load, } Q=7.3 \text{ TR}$$

Electrical class room:

Conduction heat gain through walls:

$$Q=U \times A \times \text{CLTD}_c$$

Walls	CltD	Lm	T _r (°f)	T _a (°f)	U(btu/hr-ft ² -°f)	A (sft)	CltD _c	Q (btu/hr)
East wall	14	0	50	109.6	0.0668	283	66.6	1259

Where;

$$\text{Solar time} = 14:00\text{hrs}$$

$$T_a = t_0 - DR/2 = 116.6 - 14/2$$

$$T_a = 109.6 \text{ }^\circ\text{F}$$

$$\text{CLTD}_c = \text{CLTD} + \text{LM} + (78 - T_R) + (T_a - 85)$$

$$= 14 + 0 + (78 - 50) + (109.6 - 85)$$

$$= 66.6$$

Solar radiation load for glass:

$$Q = \text{SHGF} \times A \times \text{SC} \times \text{CLF}$$

Sr.No	SHGF	A (SFT)	SC	CLF	Q (Btu/hr)
WEST GLASS	215	58.8	0.96	0.35	4247
EAST GLASS	215	24	0.96	0.31	1535

$$\text{Total} = 5782 \text{ Btu/hr}$$

Conduction heat gain through partition walls:

$$Q=U \times A \times \Delta T$$

Walls	Δt (°f)	A (sft)	U (btu/hr-ft ² f)	Q (btu/hr)
North p.wall	20	250	0.2976	1492
South p.wall	20	250	0.2976	1492
East wall	20	283	0.2624	1488
Partition roof	20	547	0.5	5478

Total = 9950 Btu/hr

Lighting load:

$$Q = 3.41 \times W \times BF \times CLF$$

$$Q = 3.41 \times 2 \times 547 \times 1.25 \times 1$$

$$Q = 4669 \text{ Btu/hr}$$

People load:

$$Q = QS + QL$$

$$QS = qs \times n \times CLF$$

$$QS = 250 \times 41 \times 1$$

$$QS = 10250 \text{ Btu/hr}$$

$$QL = qL \times n$$

$$QL = 200 \times 41$$

$$QL = 8200 \text{ Btu/hr}$$

$$Q = 10250 + 8200$$

$$Q = 18450 \text{ Btu/hr}$$

Ventilation & infiltration load:

$$Q = qs + ql$$

Estimated no. of people = 41

Min ventilation rate = 15cfm/person

Ventilation @ 5cfm/person = $15 \times 41 = 615 \text{ cfm}$

Infiltration = volume / area \times ach/60 = (floor area \times height) / floor area \times ach/60 = height \times 1/2 \times 1/60
 $= 11.4 \times 1/2 \times 1/60$
 $= 0.095 \text{ cfm/sft}$

Infiltration at 0.1cfm/sft = $0.095 \text{ cfm/sft} \times 547 = 52 \text{ cfm}$

Total ventilation and infiltration = $615 + 52 = 667 \text{ cfm}$

$Q_s = 1.10 \times \text{cfm} \times \delta t$, $Q_s = 1.10 \times 667 \times (116.6 - 75)$, $Q_s = 30521 \text{ btu/hr}$, $Q_l = 4840 \times \text{cfm} \times \delta w$
 $Q_l = 4840 \times 667 \times (0.040 - 0.030)$, $Q_l = 32282 \text{ btu/hr}$, $Q = 30521 + 32282$
 $Q = 62803 \text{ btu/hr}$

Total cooling load: = $102913 \text{ Btu/hr} = 102913/12000 = 8.5 \text{ TR}$

Add 15% F.O.S = 8.5×1.15

Total cooling load = $Q = 9.8 \text{ TR}$

Overall cooling load:

Sr.No	Space	Total load(TR)
1	Reception	7.3
2	Electrical class room	9.8
3	Total	17.1

Total = 17.1 TR

Total cooling load of building = 17.1 TR

After 15% derate = $17.1 \times 1.15 = 19.7 \text{ TR}$

Chiller capacity needed = **19.7 TR**

4. Conclusion

The study concluded that the specific HVAC cooling system could be convenient for a different section in the university. The design system estimated the total cooling load of 19.7 TR for selected buildings and piping systems were also selected for the chiller coolant unit at the top of the roof. The aim of the study was completed with the manual load calculation procedure and then the results were compared with the results obtained from the software program. It was clearly noticed and matched that the manual process of calculating the cooling load was accurate and useful for the air conditioning industry. The applied method is useful in the electronics industry for the installation of air conditioning in any environment.

References

- [1] Fischer S, CFCs dominate agenda at Chicago AS HRAE meeting, Newsleu!EA Heat Pump Centre, 7(2) (June 1989) 7-9.
- [2] Xie G, Zhou C, Wu Y, Yang Z & Zhu Z, Study of application of mixture refrigerants to small scale refrigeration equipment, /111 1 Refrig, 14(2) (199 1) 423-434.
- [3] Tillner-Roth R & Baehr H D. Measurement of propert ies in the liquid, near critical and supercritical regions of R 134a and RI 52a. H Che111 Thermodyn, 25 (1993) 277-292.

- [4] Beermann K and Kruse H Experiences with the refrigerant R 134a as a 'drop in' replacement, Proc. 11th Refrig Conf. - Efficient New Refrig, Purdue University, Indiana, US, 2 (July 14-17 1992) 211-219.
- [5] Leuckel W, Leisenheimer B & Bier K, Verbrennungstechnische Eigenschaften des Kältemittels R 152a und seiner Mischungen mit R 134a bzw R23, Ki Kiema-Kalte-Heiztl'. 4 (1992) 113-117.
- [6] Wu Y, Xie G & Li X Z, Development of a high efficiency domestic refrigerator using CFC substitutes, Int. J. Refrig. 17(3) (1994) 205-208.
- [7] Serrallach G F, Cleland A C & Cleland, Extension of an empirical method for estimating refrigeration system energy usage to new refrigerants. IIR-Commission E2 with E I, B I. B2-Melbourne. Australia- 1996 11, 1-8.
- [8] Minsan, Furkan, Y. Iwahori, and J. Huain, properties of refrigerant, International Journal of air conditioning,
- [9] Nasution, Henry, Abdul Latiff Zulkarnain, Azhar Abdul Aziz, Mohd Perang, and Mohd Rozi. "Retrofitting R-22 Split Type Air Conditioning with Hydrocarbon (HCR-22) Refrigerant." In Applied Mechanics and Materials, vol. 388, pp. 91-95. Trans Tech Publications, 2013.
- [10] Bolaji, Bukola Olalekan. "Performance of A R22 split-air-conditioner when retrofitted with ozone friendly refrigerants (R410A and R417A)." Journal of Energy in Southern Africa 23, no. 3 (2012): 16-22.
- [11] Aziz, Azridjal, and Arya Bhima Satria. "Performance of air conditioning water heater with trombone coil type as dummy condenser at different cooling loads." (2016).
- [12] Aziz, Azridjal, Rahmat Iman Mainil, and Adfhal Kurniawan Mainil. "Comparative Study of Residential Split Air Conditioner as Water Heater (RSACWH) Using R-22 and HCR-22 Refrigerant." (2015).
- [13] Aziz, Azridjal, Arya Bhima Satria, and Rahmat Iman Mainil. "Experimental study of split air conditioner with and without trombone coil condenser as air conditioning water heater." International Journal of Automotive and Mechanical Engineering 12 (2015): 3043.

Acknowledgement

I would like to thank the wonderful GOD for the grace he provided me during this study. And then I would like to express my sincere appreciation to my respected classmates and colleagues in lab for the support and guidance.

Dedication

Thanks Almighty Allah.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

© 2020 by the authors. TWASP, NY, USA. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, and data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Assets of publishing with NAAR

- Global archiving of articles
- Immediate, free online access for all
- Rigorous peer review process
- Authors retain copyrights
- DOI for all articles

<https://twasp.info/journal/home>

The graphic features a green globe with a plant growing out of it, set against a background of radiating lines.

Submit your article : editor@twasp.info